

Vacuum energy redistribution in cyclic universe of black holes

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We model bifurcation of vacuum energy (VE) near a black hole (BH) singularity into dark energy (DE) and dark matter (DM) components such that the net VE within a DM-DE halo radius vanishes. For Sgr A* the halo radius is $3.437 Mpc$, and the theory predicts results consistent with Milky Way rotation curve data out to at least $100 kpc$ if $M31^*$ perturbations are included. Analytic expressions for cosmological matter density parameters (MDP), Ω_Λ for DE and Ω_λ for DM, are derived for an ensemble of galactic black holes: At the halo radius, $\Omega_\Lambda = \Omega_\lambda$; however, at the mean galactic separation, we obtain $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.685$ and $\Omega_\lambda = 0.264$ in agreement with Planck measurements. For low galactic/BH densities, redistribution of VE by black holes results in an excess DE in the intergalactic medium which drives the accelerated expansion of the universe. The DM-DE halo formula leads to a cyclic universe of black holes (CUBH), where aeons are connected by a negative energy vacuum equilibration phase (VEP) which begins with a DM mass singularity at $26 Gyr$. The VEP mimics a wormhole, where time regresses $26 Gyr$ so that the next aeon begins at time zero in a low entropy state. The CUBH yields (a) an expression relating the Hubble constant to the halo radius of an aeon, (b) analytic results that establish a causal connection between MDPs at the DM mass singularity of one aeon and those at the next aeon's CMB, and (c) an analytic expression that reconciles CMB measurements of the Hubble constant with those derived from the local distance ladder.

I. INTRODUCTION

Astronomical observations present us with two major problems:

- The accelerated expansion of the universe suggests the presence of a vacuum-related dark energy in the intergalactic medium [1–4].
- Galactic rotation curves suggest that galaxies are surrounded by a huge amount of invisible matter in a dark matter halo [5–7].

The underlying physics behind both dark energy (DE) and dark matter (DM) is a long-standing mystery. Except for their gravitational effects, both dark energy and dark matter are invisible which suggests that they are both constituents of the vacuum. Recent observational evidence, which correlates black hole growth with the expansion of the universe [8], hints that black holes are a source of dark energy. Other observations involving DM density spikes near stellar sized black holes suggest that they could also be a source of DM [9]. In this study, we develop a model for DM and DE motivated by a theory of the quantum vacuum and redistribution of vacuum energy by singularities in QFT [10].

Ordinarily, the vacuum is defined to be the lowest energy state having no observable particles; however, as is well known, it's not empty. From a classical point of view, it's natural to assume that the vacuum is a ground state having zero energy since observed particles have positive energy relative to a zero reference level. Physically, one expects the fermion vacuum to be electrically neutral; however, according to Dirac's relativistic electron theory

[11], the existence of a stable positive energy electron implies an infinite sea of negative energy electrons, for example. Similarly, the quantized radiation field exhibits an infinite zero-point energy [12] since the field consists of an infinite number of quantum mechanical oscillators, each having a positive ground state energy. At the sub-micron level, zero-point fluctuations of the radiation field result in an attractive force between closely spaced parallel conducting plates first predicted by Casimir [13], generalized by Lifshitz [14], and subsequently confirmed by experiments [15–17]. Although ground state energies are not unexpected in quantum mechanics, an infinite vacuum energy strongly suggests that the theory is missing something. In QFT only energy differences are deemed significant, and one can just shift the energy. However, gravity accounts for all mass-energy contributions, and vacuum energy is believed to impact the accelerated expansion of the universe through the cosmological constant. In contrast to calculations for a typical quantum field, astronomical measurements suggest a vacuum energy density of only $4.8 GeV/m^3$ in the space between galaxies: This is the cosmological constant paradox discussed by Weinberg [18] for which we propose a resolution in this paper.

Standard QFT eliminates divergent ground state energies by introducing infinite renormalization constants [19, 20]. For the free fields, this is equivalent to a subtraction or a normal ordering of operators in the Hamiltonian and current density [21]: This uniquely defines a vacuum whose net energy and charge vanish. If we suppose that the infinity arising from field quantization and the renormalization constant have physical significance, then the agreement between renormalization theory predictions and experiment compels us to conclude that the vacuum must include two components for each particle of the Standard Model that oppose one another such that its net energy and charge are zero.

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As argued in detail in [10], the resolution of QFT's infinities follows simply from strict enforcement of the conservation laws. Briefly, any agent or process that does work or creates particles, real or virtual, requires a source of energy, and quantization is a process that creates an infinite sea of particles in the vacuum. Since the only known source of an infinite amount of energy (and/or charge) is the vacuum, we conclude that the required energy is sourced from the vacuum itself so that the net energy of the vacuum remains zero.

To determine the veracity of the foregoing vacuum condition, we apply it to the Casimir effect. According to QFT, boundary conditions in the Casimir experiment reduce the number of positive energy modes (PEM) between parallel plates resulting in an energy deficit within a gap of width d separating the plates.

- Key point: A PEM deficit exposes real and ever-present negative energy modes (NEM).

In the absence of interactions (boundary conditions), the net vacuum energy density

$$\rho_{vac}^{\circ} = \rho_{pem}^{\circ} + \rho_{nem} = 0 \quad (1)$$

vanishes which enables us to unambiguously compute the NEM density ρ_{nem} between the plates, where

$$\rho_{pem}^{\circ} = \frac{\hbar c}{(2\pi)^3} \int d^3k \sqrt{k_x^2 + k_y^2 + k_z^2} \quad (2)$$

is density of free PEM in the absence of the plates. It's easy to show that NEM do not interact with the plates since the amplitude to reflect (create) a negative energy particle is zero; therefore, NEM do not form standing waves. Upon introducing the plates, the net energy density

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{gap} &= \rho_{pem} + \rho_{nem} \\ &= -\frac{\pi^2 \hbar c}{720 d^4} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

within the gap involves an incomplete cancellation of divergent terms,

$$\rho_{pem} = \frac{\hbar c d^{-1}}{(2\pi)^2} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \int dk_y dk_z \sqrt{\left(\frac{2\pi n}{d}\right)^2 + k_y^2 + k_z^2} \quad (4)$$

and $\rho_{nem} = -\rho_{pem}^{\circ}$, in agreement with the subtraction method; see [22, 23], for example. For large $d \rightarrow \infty$, we recover the undisturbed vacuum whose net energy vanishes. Since $\rho_{gap} < 0$, it is a part of the vacuum that represents an interaction between PEM and the plates; thus, the net vacuum energy density

$$\rho_{vac} = \rho_{pem} + \rho_{nem} - \rho_{gap} = 0 \quad (5)$$

vanishes identically.

For the interacting fields, the infinity in the core amplitude for an irreducible radiative correction represents

energy or charge borrowed from the vacuum within limits imposed by Heisenberg's uncertainty principle [24]. In each case, there exists two physically significant vacuum components, the borrowed self-energy or charge and a corresponding deficit. In the resulting stabilized QFT [10], vacuum energy/charge is spatially redistributed such that the net correction to a scattering process is finite in the presence of external fields, but vanishes for free particles. Finite stabilized amplitudes, which agree with the on-shell renormalization scheme of standard QFT, follow from a general formula that accounts for the self-energy deficit. For the free fields, the quantum vacuum is uniformly homogeneous and isotropic, but interacting fields break the uniformity as vacuum energy is redistributed.

Vacuum bifurcation in QFT is inextricably linked to its inherent singularities. Since the Casimir effect, elementary charges, and radiative corrections all involve singularities and a redistribution of vacuum energy, we are led to inquire:

Question. *Can the gravitational singularity of a black hole redistribute vacuum energy?*

On a macroscopic scale, let us suppose that the quantum vacuum is modified near a black hole singularity to become a cosmological vacuum consisting of positive and negative energy components: DM and DE. The active gravitational mass density of DE is negative, and it is assumed gravitationally repulsive [25, 26]. In the vicinity of a black hole (BH) singularity, the BH's gravitational charge polarizes the vacuum to split it into its DM and DE components both of which include pressure terms related to a DE density via an equation of state.

Based on the foregoing considerations, we make the following assumptions:

Assumption 1. *The net energy of the cosmological vacuum is zero.*

Assumption 2. *A black hole redistributes vacuum energy to create a DM halo leaving a background DE deficit.*

Dark energy, dark matter, and their interaction are modeled as components of a cosmological vacuum whose net energy vanishes. The cosmological vacuum may include hypothetical gravitons in addition to particles of the Standard Model. Using a non-quantum approach, we account for vacuum energy density corrections near a black hole and compute halo parameters. The theory is applied to predict rotation curve profiles for the Milky Way. On a cosmic scale, galactic and cosmological density parameters are determined, the Hubble constant is related to the universe's size/mass, and a cyclic model of the universe is developed. Finally, an expression for the Hubble "constant" in the local universe is derived.

II. DARK ENERGY DENSITY

Our approach to understand the connection between dark energy and dark matter in detail begins with Einstein's field equations¹ [27–29]

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R - \Lambda_o g_{\mu\nu} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}, \quad (6)$$

where $R_{\mu\nu}$ is the Ricci tensor, $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor,

$$R = -4\Lambda_o - 8\pi G T \quad (7)$$

is the scalar curvature, $\Lambda_o > 0$ is Einstein's cosmological constant, G is the gravitational constant, and $T_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor with trace

$$T = T_{\mu}^{\mu} = \rho + 3P.$$

Density ρ and pressure P include both ordinary and dark matter contributions. Moving the cosmological term to the right side of Eq. (6), one constructs a total stress-energy tensor [30]

$$T'_{\mu\nu} = T_{\mu\nu} + \frac{\Lambda_o}{8\pi G} g_{\mu\nu}. \quad (8)$$

For weak fields ϕ and slowly moving particles, only the time component $R_{00} = \nabla^2\phi$ is non-negligible, then one obtains

$$\nabla^2\phi = 4\pi G (\rho + 3P + \rho_{\Lambda}^{\circ} g_{00}), \quad (9)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{\Lambda}^{\circ} &= \rho_{\Lambda}^{+} + 3P_{\Lambda}^{-} \\ &= -\frac{\Lambda_o}{4\pi G} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

is the active DE mass density in flat spacetime ($g_{00} = 1, g_{ij} = -\delta_{ij}$) which includes a positive part

$$\rho_{\Lambda}^{+} \equiv \Lambda_o / (8\pi G)$$

and negative pressure terms $P_{\Lambda}^{-} = -\rho_{\Lambda}^{+}$. Ordinary matter (OM) is regarded as nebular dust [31] which exerts negligible pressure in Eq. (9). In the curved spacetime near a galactic black hole, assume a Schwarzschild de Sitter (SdS) metric [32, 33]

$$ds^2 = g_{00}dt^2 - g_{00}^{-1}dr^2 - r^2d\Omega^2, \quad (11)$$

$$g_{00} = 1 - \frac{2GM}{r} - \frac{\Lambda_o}{3}r^2, \quad (12)$$

where M includes OM, DM, and DE contributions. In the absence of matter, let g_{00}^A be the contribution to the

metric from an active DE mass $M_{\Lambda} < 0$, then the DE potential satisfies

$$\nabla^2\phi_{\Lambda} = 4\pi G \rho_{\Lambda}(r), \quad (13)$$

where the DE density

$$\rho_{\Lambda}(r) = \rho_{\Lambda}^{\circ} g_{00}^A$$

and cosmological constant

$$\Lambda(r) = \Lambda_o g_{00}^A(r) \quad (14)$$

take on a spatial dependence. Within a galactic halo radius determined below, the $O(r^2)$ term in g_{00}^A is negligible², and we have

$$\rho_{\Lambda}(r) \simeq -\frac{\Lambda_o}{4\pi G} \left(1 + \frac{R_{\Lambda}}{r}\right), \quad (15)$$

where $R_{\Lambda} \equiv 2G|M_{\Lambda}|$ is an equivalent Schwarzschild radius³ that will be determined from the black hole mass, dark matter model, and dark matter density data. With this expression for $\rho_{\Lambda}(r)$, Eq. (13) admits a solution

$$\phi_{\Lambda}(r) = -\frac{\Lambda_o}{6} (r^2 + 3R_{\Lambda}r) \quad (16)$$

which will be used to derive the dark matter density below.

As well known, energy is not conserved globally in general relativity [34]; however, the energy of an isolated system (e.g., a black hole) is well defined in terms of its energy momentum four-vector, and its rest mass is an invariant. Baryon acoustic oscillation (BAO) measurements of the spatial curvature, $\Omega_k = 0.001 \pm 0.002$, indicate that the universe is very close to flat, and BAO together with Type Ia supernovae data [35] yield a dark energy equation of state parameter $w = -1.03 \pm 0.03$ which closely constrains the DE pressure $P_{\Lambda}^{-} = w\rho_{\Lambda}^{+}$ consistent with an ideal fluid in flat spacetime. In the next section, the dark matter mass density $\rho_{\lambda}(r)$ is related to a black hole mass and Λ_o ; therefore, $\rho_{\lambda}(r)$ is also well defined. In the following development, we are concerned with a static solution far from the event horizon of a black hole where spacetime is asymptotically flat. For the case of weak fields in the foregoing reduction of Einstein's field equations, ordinary Newtonian gravity may be applied. From Eq. (9), there exists well defined gravitational potentials associated with OM, DM, and DE; therefore, energy is globally conserved in the flat universe approximation.

Since introduction of Λ_o creates an omnipresent mass density ρ_{Λ}° , an opposing vacuum energy is needed to satisfy Assumption 1 and therefore conserve energy. With $\rho_{\Lambda}(r) < 0$, dark matter in ρ and dark energy oppose one another in Eq. (9), and there exists a solution such that the net energy of the cosmological vacuum vanishes.

²See Eq. (42).

³Active dark energy has a negative Schwarzschild radius, but the magnitude is taken consistent with the sign convention adopted in Eq. (15).

¹Here, we assume natural units, where the speed of light $c = 1$.

III. FORMULATION

Consider an ensemble of identical black holes in a universe where the cosmological principle holds, and assume that the gravitational charge m_{bh} of each black hole does work to redistribute vacuum energy creating a dark matter halo companion, and the ensemble generates the dark energy background. Now focus on a single black hole that is centrally located at the origin near the center of a galaxy having a spherically symmetric DM halo with unknown mass density $\rho_\lambda(r)$, where λ is a halo constant to be determined. Cosmic microwave background (CMB) radiation [36] is not included in this analysis since it is small compared to vacuum contributions, and for the moment, we neglect ordinary stellar matter.

The interaction energy density between the DM halo and $\phi_\Lambda < 0$ is given by

$$\rho_{ie} = \rho_\lambda(r) \phi_\Lambda(r). \quad (17)$$

Since $\rho_{ie} < 0$, we assume that it is uniform similarly to ρ_Λ° in flat spacetime, then we have

$$\rho_\lambda(r) = \frac{\lambda}{r^2 + R_\lambda r} \quad (R_\lambda = 3R_\Lambda), \quad (18)$$

where

$$\lambda = -\frac{6\rho_{ie}}{\Lambda_\circ}. \quad (19)$$

Dark matter and dark energy masses enclosed within radius r are

$$m_\lambda(r) = \int_0^r \rho_\lambda(r') dV(r'), \quad (20)$$

$$m_\Lambda(r) = \int_0^r \rho_\Lambda(r') dV(r'), \quad (21)$$

and the interaction mass deficit (IMD) within the halo is

$$m_{ie}(r) = \rho_{ie} V(r) / c^2. \quad (22)$$

The mass enclosed within radius r is given by

$$m_{en}(r) = m_{bh} + m_{vac}(r), \quad (23)$$

where

$$m_{vac}(r) = m_\lambda(r) + m_\Lambda(r) + m_{ie}(r) \quad (24)$$

is the vacuum part with

$$m_\lambda(r) = 4\pi\lambda r \left[1 - \frac{R_\lambda}{r} \ln \left(1 + \frac{r}{R_\lambda} \right) \right], \quad (25)$$

$$m_\Lambda(r) = -\frac{\Lambda_\circ}{3G} r^3 \left(1 + \frac{3R_\Lambda}{2r} \right), \quad (26)$$

$$m_{ie}(r) = -\frac{2\pi\lambda\Lambda_\circ}{9c^2} r^3. \quad (27)$$

To do the work required to redistribute vacuum energy, suppose that the black hole borrows its entire rest mass

energy $\mathcal{E}_{bh} = m_{bh}c^2$ from the vacuum leaving a mass deficit m_{ie} within the halo. There exists a halo radius $r = a$ such that the enclosed vacuum mass $m_{vac}(a)$ vanishes, then halo parameters follow from

$$m_{bh} + m_{ie}(a) = 0, \quad (28)$$

$$m_\lambda(a) + m_\Lambda(a) + m_{ie}(a) = 0. \quad (29)$$

The DM halo constant is given by

$$\lambda = \frac{9\mathcal{E}_{bh}}{2\pi\Lambda_\circ a^3}, \quad (30)$$

where the halo radius is a solution of

$$a^5 = a_\circ^5 \left[1 - \frac{R_\lambda}{a} \ln \left(1 + \frac{a}{R_\lambda} \right) - \epsilon(a) \right] \left(1 + \frac{3R_\Lambda}{2a} \right)^{-1} \quad (31)$$

with

$$a_\circ = \left[\frac{54G\mathcal{E}_{bh}}{\Lambda_\circ^2} \right]^{1/5}, \quad (32)$$

$$\epsilon(a) = \frac{\Lambda_\circ a^2}{18c^2} = \frac{m_{bh}}{4\pi\lambda a}. \quad (33)$$

For black holes small compared to the size of the universe, the dimensionless halo radius parameter $\epsilon(a)$ is negligible; moreover, while R_λ/a is small, its inclusion is necessary to accurately model the rotation curve near the galactic center.

When ordinary stellar matter of mass m_{om} collapses to form a BH, it is assimilated into the vacuum as DM and DE such that energy is conserved. From Eqs. (28) and (29), black hole formation and subsequent growth satisfy

$$m_{om} \rightarrow m_{en}(a) = m_\lambda(a) + m_\Lambda(a) = m_{bh}, \quad (34)$$

where $m_{om} = m_{bh} + \Delta m_r$, and Δm_r is the mass-energy radiated away during the collapse.

In Eq. (10), ρ_Λ^+ corresponds to a density of positive energy modes representing antimatter in the quantum vacuum. Using Eqs. (18), (31), and neglecting small terms R_λ and $\epsilon(a)$, the DM density in the far field of an isolated black hole is

$$\rho_\lambda(\eta) \approx -\frac{\rho_\Lambda^\circ}{3\eta^2}, \quad (35)$$

where $\eta = r/a$ is a scale factor. We conclude that DM consists of negative energy modes with density $\rho_\lambda^- \propto -\rho_\Lambda^+$ and positive pressure $P_\lambda^+ \propto -P_\Lambda^-$. Therefore, general relativity with a cosmological constant and an ensemble of black holes is consistent with a quantum vacuum composed of positive and negative energy matter including all particles of the Standard Model as defined in Appendix A of [10].

For a diverse collection of N_{bh} black holes in an approximately flat universe of volume V_u , the net energy

Table I. Astronomical Constants

Parameter	Value	Reference
H_0 [$km\ s^{-1}\ Mpc^{-1}$]	67.4 ± 0.5	[35]
Λ_0 [$10^{-35}\ s^{-2}$] = $3H_0^2$	1.43	
ρ_Λ^+ [$GeV\ m^{-3}$]	4.8	
Sun M_\odot [$10^{30}\ kg$]	1.9884 ± 0.0002	[38]
Sgr A* M_{bh} [$10^6\ M_\odot$]	4.30 ± 0.01	[39]
M31* M_{bh} [$10^8\ M_\odot$]	1.7 ± 0.6	[40]

of the cosmological vacuum is zero. From Eq. (29), we have

$$\sum_{n=1}^{N_{bh}} [m_\lambda(a_n) + m_{ie}(a_n)] + \rho_\Lambda^\circ V_u = 0, \quad (36)$$

where $a_n = a(\mathcal{E}_{bh}^n)$ for the n th black hole, and $R_\Lambda \ll a$ is assumed negligible. For a toy universe containing one black hole, $V_u \equiv V(a)$.

IV. GALACTIC RESULTS

In this section, we compute halo parameters for Milky Way (MW) black hole Sagittarius A* (Sgr A*); smaller stellar size black holes that may contribute are neglected. Rotation curves are first computed without, then with stellar matter assuming an isolated MW, and finally we include corrections due to Andromeda BH M31*. Code for generating these results is provided in [37].

Using astronomical constants in Table I and $\{R_\lambda, R_\Lambda\}$ determined below, Eqs. (31) and (30) yield

$$a = 3.437\ Mpc, \quad (37)$$

$$\lambda = 6.455 \times 10^{19}\ kg\ m^{-1} \quad (38)$$

for the halo radius and linear mass density for Sgr A*, respectively. From Eq. (17), the DM/DE-field interaction energy density is

$$\rho_{ie} = -963\ eV\ m^{-3}. \quad (39)$$

Halo parameter λ may also be estimated from Milky Way rotation curve data; over the interval 2 to 30 kpc ; the average ($6.08 \times 10^{19}\ kg\ m^{-1}$) agrees with Eq. (38) to within 6% in support of the assumption in Eq. (28).

Figure 1 (a) compares our dark matter halo density $\rho_\lambda(r)$ with results for isothermal [41, 42] and NFW [43] data models. At a solar radius of $R_\odot = 8\ kpc$, a mean of density estimates collected from the literature is indicated by a star; for values, see Table II. Assuming $R_\lambda = 0$, the dark matter density

$$\rho_\lambda(8\ kpc) = 0.593\ GeV\ cm^{-3} \quad (R_\lambda = 0) \quad (40)$$

differs significantly (by 2.6σ) from the mean in Table II; however, upon using Eq. (18),

$$R_\lambda \equiv \left(\frac{\lambda}{\rho_\lambda^\circ} - R_\odot^2 \right) / R_\odot \quad (41)$$

Table II. Local dark matter densities at solar radius.

Dark Matter Halo Model	ρ_{dm} ($GeV\ cm^{-3}$)
Isothermal	0.366
NFW	0.359
Mean [44]	0.387 ± 0.08

gives $R_\lambda = 4.251\ kpc$, where $\rho_\lambda^\circ = 0.387\ GeV\ cm^{-3}$ is the mean DM density [44]. Figure 1 (a) shows that $\rho_\lambda(r)$ agrees with the NFW density in the near-field ($r < R_\odot$), but transitions to agree with the isothermal halo density for $r > R_\odot$. Figure 1 (b) shows that the active dark energy density, $\rho_\Lambda(r)$ with $R_\Lambda = R_\lambda/3$, asymptotically approaches the flat spacetime limit for large r . Compared to our halo model, the NFW model under-estimates the enclosed halo mass in the far-field as shown in Fig. 2. Relative to the Milky Way's galactic center, spacetime goes flat at $R_f = 30.5\ Mpc$, where $g_{00}^\Lambda(R_f) = 1$; however, the approximation in Eq. (15) is adequate throughout the primary region of interest since the $O(r^2)$ and $O(r^{-1})$ terms in g_{00}^Λ satisfy

$$\frac{\Lambda_\odot r^2}{3c^2} < 1.4 \times 10^{-3} \frac{R_\Lambda}{r} \quad (0.1\ kpc \lesssim r \lesssim a). \quad (42)$$

Radius $R_\Lambda = 1.417\ kpc$ corresponds to a mass⁴

$$M_\Lambda = -\frac{R_\Lambda c^2}{2G} = -1.479 \times 10^{16}\ M_\odot; \quad (43)$$

which in magnitude dwarfs that of ordinary matter ($\lesssim 10^{11}\ M_\odot$) contributing to M in g_{00} for the Milky Way.

The circular speed of a star in an orbit of radius r is

$$v_c = \sqrt{\frac{Gm_{en}(r)}{r}}, \quad (44)$$

where

$$m_{en}(r) = m_{bh} + m_{vac}(r) + m_s(r), \quad (45)$$

is the total galactic mass enclosed, and

$$m_s = m_b + m_d + m_r \quad (46)$$

represents the enclosed mass of stars and interstellar matter: m_b , m_d , and m_r correspond to bulge, disk, and ring contributions in rotation curve models [44–47] which assume a NFW halo density.

For an isolated black hole and vacuum only, the enclosed vacuum mass and rotation curve (RC) profiles in Fig. 3 (a) and Fig. 3 (b) show that the dark matter component gives the dominant contribution for radii under

⁴Note that $R_\Lambda \gg R_s = 4.1 \times 10^{-10}\ kpc$, the Schwarzschild radius for Sgr A*, and M_Λ is equivalent to the dark energy within a sphere of radius $\sim 24.1\ Mpc$, a region exceeding the size of the Virgo Super Cluster.

Figure 1. Halo density profiles for (a) Dark matter and (b) Dark energy.

Figure 2. Enclosed dark matter halo model masses.

one megaparsec until dark vacuum energy kicks in and drives $v_c(r)$ to zero at $r = 3.437 Mpc$. The maximum vacuum mass enclosed occurs at radius

$$r_m \approx \sqrt{\frac{4\pi\lambda G}{\Lambda_\circ}} \propto m_{bh}^{1/5} \quad (47)$$

which is $1.99 Mpc$ for Sgr A*. Dark matter halo masses in Fig. 3 (a) may be compared with quasar observations [48].

Now include stellar matter with Eq. (46): Neglecting ring perturbations, bulge-2 and disk parameters [46] were adjusted to fit a more detailed model [44] in the region up to about $25 kpc$; see Table III. The resulting RC shown in Fig. 4 converges to the vacuum RC as the radius increases. Within $2.5 kpc$ of the galactic center, the DM correction in Eq. (25) brings our RC model (solid black line) into near coincidence with Sofue data (a

peak at $\sim 0.4 kpc$ and trough at $\sim 2.3 kpc$). Departures of the black-line profile from Sofue (2020) data within $25 kpc$ are due mainly to neglect of the rings. Note that the black-line profile in Fig. 4 (a) falls off more gradually than Sofue (2020) model predictions (red-dotted line with shaded uncertainty band) resulting in a significant discrepancy after approximately $30 kpc$; that said, the departure of the Sofue (2020) profile from flatness is relatively small even out to nearly $100 kpc$, and the increasing tension between the two curves indicates that corrections to the black-line profile are needed. In the outer halo region $r \gtrsim 25 kpc$, measurement uncertainties grow [47], and long range perturbations due to neighboring black holes in Andromeda and other galaxies in the local group are expected to become more important. An average correction to the squared circular velocity of a MW star due to the $M31^*$ dark matter halo is

$$\langle \delta v_c^2 \rangle = \frac{Gm_{en}^{M31^*}(r)}{r} - \frac{4\pi G\lambda_{M31^*}}{d_\circ} r \cos\theta_\circ, \quad (48)$$

where

$$m_{en}^{M31^*}(r) \approx \frac{\lambda_{M31^*}}{d_\circ^2} V(r) \quad (49)$$

accounts for dark matter enclosed within volume $V(r)$ due to $M31^*$, and the last term in Eq. (48) is determined using the virial theorem and Fig. 5. Distance d_\circ and latitude θ_\circ of $M31^*$ relative to $Sgr A^*$ are determined using galactic coordinates [49]. The total squared velocity, including the $M31^*$ perturbation, is given by

$$\langle v_c^2 \rangle = \frac{Gm_{en}^{MW}(r)}{r} + \langle \delta v_c^2 \rangle, \quad (50)$$

where m_{en}^{MW} is the enclosed Milky Way mass. The approximately linear increase in DM halo mass shown in

Fig. 2 results in a nearly constant contribution

$$v_\lambda^2 = Gm_\lambda(r)/r$$

to v_c^2 tending to sustain a nearly level RC profile as shown in Fig. 4; however, the $M31^*$ correction $\langle \delta v_c^2 \rangle < 0$ in Fig. 6 (a) opposes v_λ^2 reducing the orbital energy of a Milky Way star to produce results in close agreement with the Sofue RC which employs the NFW halo model⁵. The rings contribution included in Fig. 6 (a) is well approximated as the difference between RCs with rings [44] and without [46]. For a mean $M31^*$ mass $1.7 \times 10^8 M_\odot$ from Table I, $v_c \rightarrow 0$ at approximately 209 kpc in Fig. 6 (b).

For the local universe, it may be more appropriate to use H_o from the SHOES program [50]. In that case, we obtain the halo parameters shown in Table IV, and we find that the corresponding rotation curves are nearly indistinguishable from those in Fig. 6 which assume the Planck value for H_o .

V. COSMOLOGICAL MATTER DENSITY PARAMETERS

For a toy universe of N_g Milky Way-like galaxies, Eq. (36) simplifies to

$$N_g(4\pi\lambda a - m_{bh}) + \rho_\Lambda^\circ V_u = 0 \quad (51)$$

resulting in a mean galactic density

$$\rho_g = -\frac{\rho_\Lambda^\circ}{4\pi\lambda a} (1 - \epsilon)^{-1} \quad (52)$$

where $\epsilon \ll 1$ is negligible, and $\rho_g \approx 0.00583 Mpc^{-3}$. This result is consistent with Schechter normalization densities ϕ^* for dark matter dominated spheroidal type galaxies [51–55]. The mean galactic separation

$$d_g = \rho_g^{-1/3} \approx \left(\frac{4\pi}{3}\right)^{1/3} a \quad (53)$$

yields $d_g = 5.54 Mpc$. Since $\mathcal{E}_{bh} \propto d_g^5$, an expanding universe is consistent with black hole growth in agreement with recent observations [8].

Using Eq. (35) and neglecting ρ_{ie} , the total vacuum energy density

$$\rho_{vac}(\eta = r/a) \simeq \rho_\lambda(\eta) + \rho_\Lambda^\circ \quad (54)$$

goes negative when $r \gtrsim a/\sqrt{3}$. For a sufficiently small density of galaxies containing black holes, the enclosed mass $m_{en}(r)$ goes negative for $r > a$, the radial acceleration $\ddot{r} \approx -Gm_{en}/r^2$ of a test mass is positive, and

we expect cosmic acceleration on average. In general, we expect that $\rho_\Lambda(r) \lesssim \rho_{vac} < 0$ in regions far from black holes, but the condition $\rho_{vac} \geq 0$ will only be satisfied near black holes where $r \lesssim a/\sqrt{3}$.

For each type of mass-energy, cosmological matter density parameters (MDP) or mass fractions are defined by

$$\Omega_i(r) = \frac{|m_i(r)|}{m_{tot}(r)} \quad (i = om, \lambda, \Lambda, rad) , \quad (55)$$

where $m_i(r)$ are masses enclosed within radius r , and

$$m_{tot}(r) = m_\lambda(r) + |m_\Lambda(r)| + m_{om}(r) + m_{rad}(r) . \quad (56)$$

Neglecting a small contribution due to radiation Ω_{rad} , MDPs for dark matter Ω_λ and dark energy Ω_Λ within radius r are given by

$$\Omega_i(r) = [1 - \Omega_{om}(r)] \frac{|m_i(r)|}{m_\lambda(r) + |m_\Lambda(r)|} \quad (i = \lambda, \Lambda) , \quad (57)$$

where Ω_{om} accounts for ordinary matter in stellar and intergalactic media, and is assumed known. At $r = d_g$,

$$\Omega_{om}(d_g) \equiv \Omega_{om}^p \quad (58)$$

is determined from Planck Collaboration data [35] given in Table V. For simplicity's sake, assume a uniform distribution of ordinary matter for $r < d_g$, then

$$\Omega_{om}(r) = (r/d_g)^3 \Omega_{om}^p . \quad (59)$$

Figure 7 shows MDP profiles for $\Omega_\lambda(r)$ and $\Omega_\Lambda(r)$, where $\Omega_\lambda \simeq \Omega_\Lambda$ at $r = a$; however, at $r = d_g$ we have

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Omega_\lambda \\ \Omega_\Lambda \end{bmatrix}_{r=d_g} = \frac{(1 - \Omega_{om}^p)}{1 + \beta} \begin{bmatrix} \beta \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.2637 \\ 0.6852 \end{bmatrix} , \quad (60)$$

where

$$\beta = \frac{m_\lambda}{|m_\Lambda|} \Big|_{r=d_g} = \left(\frac{3}{4\pi}\right)^{2/3} . \quad (61)$$

Results in Eq. (60) are within Planck data 1-sigma uncertainties given in Table V; therefore, $\Omega_c^p \sim \Omega_\lambda$ and Ω_Λ^p in Table V reflect effective values at the mean galactic separation. Note that Eq. (60) is only weakly dependent on Ω_{om}^p , and it is independent of any particular ensemble of black holes. While the mean galactic separation $d_g = 5.54 Mpc$ in Fig. 7 corresponds to a Sgr A* black hole, $\Omega_\lambda(d_g)$ and $\Omega_\Lambda(d_g)$ are constants for any ensemble of black holes with arbitrary m_{bh} and corresponding d_g .

VI. FRIEDMANN EQUATIONS

The standard model of cosmology connects the cosmological constant with ordinary and cold dark matter

⁵The NFW model effectively accounts for both dark energy and dark matter from all sources.

Table III. Stellar matter parameters.

Component	Parameter	Adjusted
Bulge 1	$a_b = 3.5 pc$ $M_b = 0.4 \times 10^8 M_\odot$	-
Bulge 2	$a_b = 120 pc$ $M_b = 0.92 \times 10^{10} M_\odot$	$a_b = 165 pc$ $M_b = 1.15 \times 10^{10} M_\odot$
Disk	$a_d = 4.9 kpc$ $M_d = 0.9 \times 10^{11} M_\odot$	$a_d = 4.8 kpc$ $M_d = 0.95 \times 10^{11} M_\odot$

† Total includes small contribution from interaction energy m_{ie} .

Figure 3. (a) Enclosed vacuum masses for an isolated Milky Way BH Sgr A*. (b) Sgr A* rotation curve.

Table IV. Milky Way halo parameters using H_\odot^{SHOES} from [50].

Parameter	Value
$H_\odot^{SHOES} [km s^{-1} Mpc^{-1}]$	73.04 ± 1.04
$\Lambda_\odot^{SHOES} [10^{-35} s^{-2}]$	1.685
$a [Mpc]$	3.222
$\lambda [10^{19} kg m^{-1}]$	6.671
$R_\lambda [kpc]$	1.551
$R_\lambda [kpc]$	4.652

Table V. Planck Collaboration Data with $1-\sigma$ uncertainties σ_i^p .

Planck MDP	Value
Ω_b^p (baryons)	0.049243 ± 0.000330
Ω_c^p (dark matter)	0.264157 ± 0.002642
Ω_Λ^p (dark energy)	0.684700 ± 0.007300
Ω_m^p (matter)	0.315300 ± 0.007300
Ω_{rad}^p (radiation)†	$9.26 \times 10^{-5} \pm 7.08 \times 10^{-7}$
z_{eq}	3402 ± 26
$\Omega_{om}^p = \Omega_m - \Omega_c$	0.051143 ± 0.007763

† $\Omega_{rad}^p = \Omega_m^p / (1 + z_{eq})$

[56–58]. It is based on the Friedmann equations [59, 60]

$$\left(H = \frac{\dot{\alpha}}{\alpha}\right)^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{3}\rho - \frac{kc^2}{d^2} + \frac{\Lambda_\odot}{3}, \quad (62)$$

$$\frac{\ddot{\alpha}}{\alpha} = -\frac{4\pi G}{3}(\rho + 3P + \rho_\Lambda^\circ), \quad (63)$$

where H is the Hubble parameter, $\alpha(t)$ is the cosmic scale factor (CSF) at epoch time t , and k is the curvature. The proper distance between two objects or events at time t is

$$d(t) = \alpha(t) d_\circ,$$

where d_\circ is a comoving distance reference defined at the current epoch t_\circ , and $\alpha(t_\circ) = 1$. The left side of Eq. (62) embodies the Hubble-Lemaître law [61–63]. In Eq. (63), the condition for an accelerating universe is [30]

$$\rho + 3P + \rho_\Lambda^\circ < 0. \quad (64)$$

For small mass density and pressure due to ordinary and dark matter, Eq. (64) reduces to $\rho_{vac} < 0$.

Given Eq. (60), the evolution of the Hubble parameter

$$H(\alpha) = H_\circ [\Omega(\alpha)]^{1/2}, \quad (65)$$

$$\Omega(\alpha) = \Omega_\Lambda + \Omega_k \alpha^{-2} + (\Omega_{om} + \Omega_\lambda) \alpha^{-3} + \Omega_{rad} \alpha^{-4} \quad (66)$$

Figure 4. Rotation curves for Milky Way galaxy including BH Sgr A*, vacuum, and stellar matter.

Figure 5. $M31^*$ correction to kinetic energy of a MW star in a plane containing black holes $Sgr A^*$ and $M31^*$.

reduces mainly to determining Ω_{om} , where H_o is the Hubble constant,

$$\alpha = \frac{d(t)}{d_o} = \frac{1}{1+z}, \quad (67)$$

z is the red shift parameter, and $H(\alpha=1) = H_o$. The primordial singularity, or Big Bang (BB), corresponds to infinite red shift or CSF $\alpha = 0$. Since experiment [35] suggests that the global topology of the universe is flat, we set the curvature density parameter Ω_k to zero.

In the next section, we derive an analytic expression for Ω_{om} , and formulae given below will be needed to evaluate cosmological distances and times. The elapsed cosmic time and comoving distance at time t from scale factor α_i to $\alpha_f(t)$ are

$$T(\alpha_i, \alpha_f) = \int_{\alpha_i}^{\alpha_f} \frac{d\alpha}{\alpha^2 H(\alpha)}, \quad (68)$$

$$d_{cm}(\alpha_i, \alpha_f) = c \int_{\alpha_i}^{\alpha_f} \frac{d\alpha}{\alpha^2 H(\alpha)}, \quad (69)$$

where

$$\alpha_i = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{BB} \\ \alpha(z_*) & \text{PD} \end{cases}, \quad (70)$$

and z_* = 1090 is the red shift parameter at the epoch of photon decoupling (PD); see [35, 64]. The corresponding particle horizon (PH) distance is

$$d_{ph} = \alpha_f d_{cm}. \quad (71)$$

An observer's knowledge of an event happening now is limited to distances less than the current cosmic event horizon (CEH), $d_o \equiv R_{ceh}(t_o)$, where [65, 66]

$$R_{ceh}(t) = c\alpha(t) \int_{\alpha(t)}^{\infty} \frac{d\alpha}{\alpha^2 H(\alpha)}. \quad (72)$$

VII. CYCLIC UNIVERSE OF BLACK HOLES

Here, we develop a cyclic model of the universe consisting of an expansion phase involving black hole growth with redistribution of vacuum energy followed by a BH disintegration and vacuum equilibration phase where DM and DE recombine to produce a hot uniform plasma of ordinary matter.

In a comoving frame of reference, the observable universe is static apart from peculiar motions; therefore, nothing escapes, and it mimics a Schwarzschild black hole. So, let us begin by applying the DM-DE halo formula (31) with $R_A = 0$ to relate the Hubble constant to

Figure 6. Milky Way rotation curve with M31* correction. Ring contribution are included in (a), but not in (b)..

Figure 7. Matter density parameters for dark matter Ω_λ and dark energy Ω_Λ near Sgr A* black hole.

the mass of a Schwarzschild universe (SU) with an event horizon having radius [67]

$$a \rightarrow a_{su} \equiv \frac{2GM_{su}}{c^2} \quad (73)$$

which becomes a solution to

$$a_{su}^4 + \delta b^4 a_{su}^2 - b^4 = 0, \quad (74)$$

where

$$b^4 = \frac{27c^4}{\Lambda_o^2}, \quad (75)$$

and $\delta = \Lambda_o / (18c^2)$. While δ is small, $\epsilon = \delta a_{su}^2$ may not be neglected. Eq. (74) reduces to a quadratic in ϵ

$$\epsilon^2 + \frac{1}{12}\epsilon - \frac{1}{12} = 0 \quad (76)$$

whose positive solution is $\epsilon = 1/4$. In terms of $\Lambda_o = 3H_o^2$, it follows that

$$a_{su} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2}} \frac{c}{H_o}, \quad (77)$$

$$M_{su} = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{3}{2}} \frac{c^3}{H_o G}. \quad (78)$$

Using the Planck value for H_o in Table I, we have

$$a_{su} = 17.759 \text{ Gly}, \quad (79)$$

$$M_{su} = 1.131 \times 10^{53} \text{ kg}. \quad (80)$$

Notice that $a_{su} \simeq R_{ceh}^\infty$, the CEH in the distant future

$$R_{ceh}^\infty = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} R_{ceh}(t) \quad (81)$$

$$= \frac{c}{H_o} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\Omega_\Lambda}} = 17.525 \text{ Gly}. \quad (82)$$

Mass M_{su} should be compared with other methods [68–71] which also give masses of order 10^{53} kg . Using

$$H_o^{SHOES} = 73.04 \pm 1.04 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1} \quad (83)$$

from Table IV, we obtain

$$a_{su}^{SHOES} = 16.388 \text{ Gly}, \quad (84)$$

$$M_{su}^{SHOES} = 1.043 \times 10^{53} \text{ kg}. \quad (85)$$

Radius a_{su}^{SHOES} is close to the current CEH

$$R_{ceh}^\circ = 16.674 \text{ Gly} \quad (86)$$

which is not surprising since H_o^{SHOES} is derived from the local distance ladder. Since $H_o \propto M_{su}^{-1}$ from Eq. (78), the larger mass within a_{su} reduces the expansion rate of the Planck H_o relative to that for SHOES; therefore, the Hubble tension [50] corresponds to a lower mass of the universe within R_{ceh}° .

Now relax the condition that matter is confined within the SU/CEH, and assume that the universe expands into the region $R > a_{su}$, where $\epsilon > 1/4$. On a global scale the expanding universe is akin to a white hole composed of black holes. Solving Eq. (31) for the BH mass, the halo radius and mass parameters expressed in terms of ϵ are

$$R(\epsilon) = \sqrt{6\epsilon} \frac{c}{H_o}, \quad (87)$$

$$M(\epsilon) = \frac{6c^2}{G} \frac{\epsilon^2}{1-\epsilon} R(\epsilon), \quad (88)$$

where subscripts are omitted. For $\epsilon = 1/4$, we recover Eqs. (77) and (78). The mass singularity (MS) at $\epsilon_{ms} = 1$ corresponds to a critical halo radius

$$R_{ms} = 2a_{su} = 35.518 \text{ Gly}. \quad (89)$$

From Eqs. (78) and (88), we have

$$M(\epsilon) = 24M_{su} \frac{\epsilon^{5/2}}{1-\epsilon}. \quad (90)$$

Since the BH universe mass $M(\epsilon \rightarrow 1^-) \rightarrow \infty$, the expansion phase comes to a halt at $\epsilon_{ms} = 1$. The derivative

$$\frac{dM}{d\epsilon} = 12M_{su}\epsilon^{3/2} \frac{5-3\epsilon}{(1-\epsilon)^2}, \quad (91)$$

reveals that $M(\epsilon)$ has horizontal inflections at

$$\epsilon = \{0, 5/3\}$$

which suggests that these points may mark consecutive Big Bang (BB) events. Taking into account Eq. (77), the spacial period of an aeon in halo measure is given by

$$\begin{aligned} R_{aeon} &= R(5/3) = 2\sqrt{\frac{5}{3}}a_{su} \\ &= 45.85 \text{ Gly}. \end{aligned} \quad (92)$$

At first one may find that the agreement between R_{aeon} and the comoving distance

$$d_{cm}(BB \rightarrow t_o) = 46.1 \text{ Gly}$$

from the last BB to the current epoch surprising, but it is just a statement that the comoving size of the universe is constant. To good approximation, the mean distance between Big Bangs of consecutive universes may be obtained using the same rule as that between galaxies containing black holes. Taking into account Eqs. (53) and (61), making the replacement

$$\alpha(t) = \frac{d(t)}{d_o} \rightarrow \alpha'(t) = \frac{\alpha(t)}{\sqrt{\beta}} \quad (93)$$

in Eq. (72), and taking the limit $\alpha(t) \rightarrow \infty$, we have

$$R'_{aeon} = \frac{r}{\beta} = \begin{cases} 45.54 & r = R_{ceh}^\infty \\ 46.15 & r = a_{su} \end{cases} \quad (94)$$

which bounds the result for R_{aeon} in Eq. (92) and has mean value $R'_{aeon} = 45.84 \text{ Gly}$. Together, these results suggest a fundamental connection between the maximum halo radius R_{aeon} and the cosmic event horizon.

Expanding Eq. (92) using (77) yields

$$H_o = 2\sqrt{\frac{5}{2}} \frac{c}{R_{aeon}} \quad (95)$$

which is equivalent to Eq. (78) involving M_{su} . Thus, H_o depends on the entirety of an aeon within which the net energy of the vacuum vanishes, and it is in close proximity to the next aeon's CMB. In terms of an aeon's halo radius, the cosmological constant is

$$\Lambda_o = 30 \frac{c^2}{R_{aeon}^2}. \quad (96)$$

Expansion of the universe to a critical halo radius R_{ms} marks the onset of a highly turbulent vacuum equilibration phase (VEP) on the interval $1 < \epsilon \leq 5/3$, where we hypothesize that BH masses m_{bh} recombine with interaction mass deficits m_{ie} created when energy was originally borrowed from the vacuum to create DM halos and DE background. Once the tension holding DM halos to individual black holes is released in the vicinity of ϵ_{ms} , DM potential energy is converted to thermal energy as the vacuum equilibrates until the net vacuum energy vanishes per the requirement in Eq. (36) leaving a hot nearly uniform plasma of ordinary matter in volume $V(R_{aeon})$ with small temperature fluctuations [64]. For simultaneous disintegration of black holes at R_{ms} , the collection of black holes are supposed to be entangled via vacuum energy such that they act as a unified black hole. Continuity at the next Big Bang event is achieved by integrating Eq. (91) to obtain

$$M_{vep}(\epsilon) = M(\epsilon) + \Delta M_{BB} \quad (1 < \epsilon \leq 5/3), \quad (97)$$

where the integration constant

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta M_{BB} &\equiv -M(5/3) \\ &= 100\sqrt{\frac{5}{3}}M_{su} \end{aligned} \quad (98)$$

is chosen to satisfy the boundary condition

$$M_{vep}(5/3) = M(0) \quad (99)$$

at the next Big Bang. From Eq. (29) with $m \rightarrow M$, we see that

$$\Delta M_{BB} = M_{ie}(R_{aeon}) \quad (100)$$

must represent a positive interaction mass deficit (IMD) that ensures Assumption 1 is satisfied at the halo radius of an aeon.

Figure 8 (a) shows BH universe mass profiles over an aeon period. In Fig. 8 (b), DM and DE masses enclosed within radius $R(\epsilon)$ are given by

$$M_\lambda^{en}(\epsilon) = 4\pi\lambda R(\epsilon) = \frac{M(\epsilon)}{\epsilon} \quad (\epsilon < 1), \quad (101)$$

$$M_A^{en}(\epsilon) = M_\lambda^{en}(\epsilon)(\epsilon - 1), \quad (102)$$

where

$$M(\epsilon) \rightarrow M_{vep}(\epsilon) \quad (\epsilon > 1) \quad (103)$$

in the VEP. From Fig. 8 (b), DE is continuous at ϵ_{ms} , but the asymptotically singular DM profile changes sign so that the negative mass-energy

$$M_{vep}(\epsilon) = M_{\lambda}^{\epsilon n}(\epsilon) + M_{\Lambda}^{\epsilon n}(\epsilon) \quad (104)$$

forms a wormhole-like conduit connecting two aeons.

The net BH mass discontinuity

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta M_{ms} &\equiv \lim_{\delta \rightarrow 0} [M(1-\delta) + M(1+\delta)] \\ &= -120 M_{su} \end{aligned} \quad (105)$$

at the singularity accounts for most of the mass deficit $M(5/3)$ in Eq. (98). Taking into account Dirichlet's theorem, the mass residual

$$\begin{aligned} M_{om}(\epsilon_{ms}) &= [\Delta M_{BB} + \Delta M_{ms}] / 2 \\ &= 4.55 M_{su} \end{aligned} \quad (106)$$

is identified as ordinary matter since it allows us to accurately predict OM, DM, and DE MDPs at the next aeon's CMB and at the current epoch. Mass M_{om} accounts only for ordinary matter released upon BH disintegration, where DM and DE recombine to release OM back into the universe in essentially the time reversal of Eq. (34)

$$M_{\lambda}(\epsilon_{ms}) + M_{\Lambda}(\epsilon_{ms}) \rightarrow M_{om}(\epsilon_{ms}) . \quad (107)$$

The VEP is likened to a white hole with a singularity at ϵ_{ms} since ordinary matter is sourced there.

Evolution of the MDPs and Hubble parameter is determined from the Friedmann equations; for CSF α in the expansion or BH growth phase, we have

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Omega_{\Lambda} \\ \Omega_{\lambda} \\ \Omega_{om} \\ \Omega_{rad} \end{bmatrix}_{\alpha} = \frac{1}{\Omega(\alpha)} \begin{bmatrix} \Omega_{\Lambda}^p \alpha^{-3} \\ \Omega_{\lambda}^p \alpha^{-3} \\ \Omega_{om}^p \alpha^{-3} \\ \Omega_{rad}^p \alpha^{-4} \end{bmatrix} \quad (\epsilon < 1) . \quad (108)$$

where $\alpha(\epsilon)$ is defined by Eq. (123), $\Omega(\alpha)$ is given by Eq. (66), and the MDPs Ω_i^p for the current epoch are taken from Table V.

Since $M_{om}(\epsilon_{ms})$ is known from Eq. (106), adjusted MDPs at the mass singularity are defined by

$$\Omega_i(\epsilon) = \left. \frac{|M_i(\epsilon)|}{M_{tot}(\epsilon)} \right|_{\epsilon=\epsilon_{ms}} \quad (i = om, \lambda, \Lambda, rad) , \quad (109)$$

where $M_i(\epsilon)$ are masses enclosed within halo radius parameter ϵ ,

$$M_{tot}(\epsilon) = M_{\lambda}(\epsilon) + |M_{\Lambda}(\epsilon)| + M_{om}(\epsilon) + M_{rad}(\epsilon) , \quad (110)$$

$$\begin{aligned} M_{\Lambda}(\epsilon) &= \rho_{\Lambda}^{\circ} V(R(\epsilon)) \\ &= M(\epsilon)(\epsilon - 1) / \epsilon , \end{aligned} \quad (111)$$

$$M_{\lambda}(\epsilon) = -\beta M_{\Lambda}(\epsilon) , \quad (112)$$

and β is given by Eq. (61). The enclosed radiation mass is given by

$$M_{rad} = \rho_{\gamma\nu}(\theta_{ms}) V(R(\epsilon)) , \quad (113)$$

where $\rho_{\gamma\nu}(\theta_{ms})$ includes photon and neutrino mass densities at temperature θ_{ms} ; see [29]. Evaluating Eq. (109) for OM, DM, and DE MDPs, we have

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Omega_{om} \\ \Omega_{\lambda} \\ \Omega_{\Lambda} \end{bmatrix}_{\epsilon_{ms}} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.1204 \\ 0.2444 \\ 0.6351 \end{bmatrix} . \quad (114)$$

Then, from Fig. 9 (a) and Fig. 9 (b), we find that MDPs at the mass singularity causally map into those at photon decoupling (PD) in the next aeon according to

$$DE_n(MS) \rightarrow DM_{n+1}(PD) , \quad (115)$$

$$DM_n(MS) \rightarrow Rad_{n+1}(PD) , \quad (116)$$

$$OM_n(MS) \rightarrow OM_{n+1}(PD) , \quad (117)$$

where n denotes the aeon number. In particular, Eq. (116) supports the hypothesis that DM energy at the mass singularity morphs into the radiation of a hot, thermalized plasma at the next aeon's CMB. From Eqs. (65) and (95), the Hubble parameter is also causally connected to the previous aeon.

Assuming that no black holes form during the VEP, the initial OM mass at the Big Bang is

$$M_{om}(BB) = M_{om}(\epsilon_{ms}) . \quad (118)$$

If subsequent BH growth is sourced from ordinary matter within halo radius $R(\epsilon)$, the OM mass at the current epoch t_{\circ} corresponding to $\alpha = 1$ or $\epsilon_{\circ} = \epsilon(R_{ceh}^{\circ})$ is

$$M_{om}(\epsilon) = \rho_{om}(\epsilon) V(R(\epsilon)) \quad (\epsilon = \epsilon_{\circ}) , \quad (119)$$

$$\rho_{om}(\epsilon) = \frac{M_{om}(BB) - M(\epsilon)}{V(R_{aeon})} . \quad (120)$$

Then, evaluating Eq. (109) at $\epsilon = \epsilon_{\circ}$ gives

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Omega'_{om} \\ \Omega'_{\lambda} \\ \Omega'_{\Lambda} \end{bmatrix}_{\epsilon_{\circ}} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.0511 \\ 0.2637 \\ 0.6852 \end{bmatrix} \quad (121)$$

along with a small radiation contribution of 9.27×10^{-5} , all in agreement with Planck data. Figure 10 shows that MDP errors

$$\delta \Omega_i = \frac{\Omega'_i(M_{om}) - \Omega_i^{ref}}{\sigma_i^p} \quad (122)$$

are sensitive to perturbations in the initial OM mass in Eq. (120), where σ_i^p are Planck 1-sigma errors, and Ω_i^{ref}

Figure 8. (a) Total BH universe mass enclosed. (b) DM/DE mass enclosed.

Figure 9. (a) MDP profiles from photon decoupling to mass singularity for DE, DM, and OM. (b) Radiation MDP.

is a MDP reference best determined from Eq. (60) for consistency. For $\alpha \neq 1$, Eq. (108) is used to propagate MDPs Ω'_i in the usual way. This completes justification for the physical interpretation in Eq. (106).

Since the halo radius $R(\epsilon)$ is assumed to move with the Hubble flow, the scale factor is defined by

$$\alpha(\epsilon) = \frac{R(\epsilon)}{R_{ceh}^o} \quad (123)$$

for computation of cosmological times and horizons. At end of an aeon, we have

$$\alpha_{aeon} = \frac{R_{aeon}}{R_{ceh}^o} = 2.75, \quad (124)$$

and the CEH halo radius

$$R_{ceh}(\alpha_{aeon}) = 17.48 \text{ Gly} \quad (125)$$

is in close agreement with R_{ceh}^∞ in Eq. (82). From Eq. (68), the VEP is estimated to begin after an elapsed cosmological time of

$$T_{ms} = T(0, \alpha_{ms}) = 26.01 \text{ Gyr}, \quad (126)$$

where

$$\alpha_{ms} = \frac{R_{ms}}{R_{ceh}^o} = 2.13. \quad (127)$$

Utilizing Eq. (65), but taking the negative square root, the Hubble parameter during the VEP is defined by

$$H_{vep}(\alpha) = -H_{ms} \sqrt{\Omega_A^{vep} + \Omega_m^{vep} \alpha^{-3} + \Omega_{rad}^{vep} \alpha^{-4}}, \quad (128)$$

where

$$H_{ms} = H_o [\Omega(\alpha_{ms})]^{1/2} \quad (129)$$

Figure 10. MDP sensitivity to perturbations in OM mass at Big Bang.

is the initial value at the mass singularity, and

$$\Omega_m^{vep} = \Omega_\lambda^{vep} + \Omega_{om}^{vep}.$$

Assuming that MDPs $\{\Omega_\lambda^{vep}, \Omega_m^{vep}\}$ are negligible compared to that for radiation in the ultra-hot VEP,

$$\Omega_{rad}^{vep} \equiv 1.$$

Then, from Eq. (68), the duration of the VEP is

$$\Delta T_{vep} = -\frac{\alpha_{aeon}^2 - \alpha_{ms}^2}{2H_{ms}}. \quad (130)$$

Using Planck values for H_o from Table I and MDPs from Table V, we have

$$H_{ms}^\circ = 57.08 \text{ km/s/Mpc}, \quad (131)$$

$$\Delta T_{vep}^\circ = -25.90 \text{ Gyr}, \quad (132)$$

which takes us back to about 0.11 *Gyr* of the Big Bang; therefore, the net duration of an aeon is zero to within 0.5%. Perhaps T_{aeon} 's proximity to zero is just a coincidence, but it may indeed vanish identically. Notice that

$$H_{ms} = 56.83 \text{ km/s/Mpc} \quad (133)$$

gives

$$T_{aeon} = T_{ms} + \Delta T_{vep} = 0, \quad (134)$$

and the relative error between H_{ms}° and H_{ms} is consistent with H_o and MDP uncertainties if we hold T_{ms} and the scale factors in Eq. (130) constant; for example, a $0.6 \sigma_H$ reduction in H_o or

$$H_o' = 67.10 \text{ km/s/Mpc} \quad (135)$$

Figure 11. Dependence of T_{aeon} on Hubble constant and OM uncertainties.

satisfies Eq. (134). For MDP variations we neglect radiation, hold H_o constant, and vary Ω_{om} only since Ω_Λ for DE and Ω_λ for DM may be determined from Eq. (60). Figure 11 results show that zeros for T_{aeon} are within 1-sigma uncertainties for both H_o and Ω_{om} . If entropy varies strictly in accordance with the arrow of time, and the net duration of an aeon is zero, then a relatively small entropy is expected at each Big Bang. Apart from differences in formulation and physical interpretation, the essential conclusion that the universe is cyclic with low entropy at the Big Bang is consistent with Penrose's theory [72, 73] of conformal cyclic cosmology (CCC).

Assuming natural Planck units, let us suppose that Hawking's expressions for BH entropy [74]

$$S = 4\pi\mathcal{M}^2, \quad (136)$$

and temperature

$$\Theta = \frac{1}{8\pi\mathcal{M}} \quad (137)$$

of a BH are applicable to our cyclic universe of black holes, where

$$\mathcal{M} \equiv \begin{cases} M(\epsilon) & \epsilon < 1 \\ M(\epsilon) - M(5/3) & 1 < \epsilon < 5/3 \end{cases} \quad (138)$$

accounts for the VEP adjustment in Eq. (103). Then from Fig. 8 (a), the BH entropy is zero at the beginning and end of each cycle (Big Bangs). From Eq. (137) and Fig. 8 (a), the VEP has negative temperature [75, 76], where

$$\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 5/3} \Theta(\epsilon) = -\infty \quad (139)$$

as the universe approaches the next Big Bang. Twenty-six *Gyr* of ultra-hot temperatures in the VEP are expected to result in a highly thermalized primordial

plasma after the next Big Bang that is consistent with CMB observations [77]. If indeed the last equality in Eq. (134) holds true, then the universe is fine tuned to remarkable precision: Black hole entropy and cosmological time are simultaneously zero at each Big Bang and maximum at the mass singularity.

Assuming $T_{aeon} = 0$ at the end of the VEP (start of the next BB), the particle horizon and scale factor are reset to zero for consistency. However, using Eqs. (69) and (133), we have

$$d_{ph}(0, \alpha_{aeon}) = d_{ph}(0, \alpha_{ms}) + \Delta d_{ph}^{vep}, \quad (140)$$

where

$$\Delta d_{ph}^{vep} = -\frac{c\alpha_{aeon}}{H_{ms}} (\alpha_{aeon} - \alpha_{ms}).$$

The particle horizon decreases by only 29 *Gly* during the VEP, so like Penrose's CCC there is no "Big Crunch". In the ultra-hot VEP plasma, no visible structures are likely to endure; therefore, the particle horizon loses its observational significance relative to the last BB, and we are well justified in setting it to zero at the end of an aeon. Nevertheless, the halo radius continues to increase until its maximum value R_{aeon} is achieved at the next Big Bang, where the condition in Eq. (36) is satisfied.

Table VI gives a timeline from start to end of an aeon, and Fig. 12 displays cosmological time and black hole entropy profiles from which we conclude that the universe models a precision cosmological clock.

VIII. HUBBLE TENSION

To reconcile CMB measurements of the Hubble constant H_o with those derived from the local distance ladder, we need to include the $O(r^2)$ term in g_{00}^A . From Eq. (14), the Hubble constant assumes a spatial dependence

$$H(r, H_o) = H_o \sqrt{1 + \frac{R_A}{r} - (H_o r/c)^2}. \quad (141)$$

Recall from Eq. (94) that R_{ceh}^∞ maps into R_{aeon}

$$R_{ceh}^\infty \xrightarrow{\beta^{-1}} R_{aeon} \quad (142)$$

which is near the next CMB in the cyclic model; in addition, Eq. (125) defines a more precise inverse mapping. Therefore, with respect to the previous aeon, $r \simeq R_{ceh}^\infty$ locates the Big Bang and adjacent CMB with sufficient precision. Since BAO measurements indicate a spatially-flat universe at the CMB, we have $g_{00}^A(R_{ceh}^\infty) = 1$, $H(R_{ceh}^\infty) = H_o$, and

$$\begin{aligned} R_A &= (H_o R_{ceh}^\infty/c)^2 R_{ceh}^\infty \\ &= 25.6 \text{ Gly}. \end{aligned} \quad (143)$$

In the local universe where $r = R_{ceh}^\circ$, the dependence of $H(R_{ceh}^\circ, H_o')$ on the erred value

$$H_o' = H_o (1 + n\sigma_H) \quad (144)$$

at the CMB is shown in Fig. 13. For $n = 0$, compare

$$H_{local} = 74.23 \text{ km/s/Mpc} \quad (145)$$

with the SH0E's value in Eq. (83) and recent measurements of the nearby Coma Cluster obtained by the Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument (DESI) collaboration [78].

IX. CONCLUSIONS

Evidence presented for black hole cosmology supports the hypothesis that BH singularities redistribute vacuum energy in the cosmos. The same assumptions that resolve divergence issues in QFT without renormalization applied to black holes leads to a DM-DE halo formula that explains how black holes split the vacuum into dark matter, dark energy, and DM-DE interaction terms such that the net vacuum energy within the halo vanishes; in consequence, a supermassive BH near the center of a galaxy polarizes the vacuum resulting in nearly flat rotation curves out to vast distances within the halo where the enclosed DM greatly exceeds that of DE.

Applied to the universe at large, the DM-DE halo formula provides a physical mechanism for genesis of a Big Bang from a vacuum equilibration phase (VEP), and a cyclic model of the universe is predicted similarly to Penrose's CCC. The VEP begins at a mass singularity where entangled black holes disintegrate, and the Big Bang marks an event where vacuum equilibration is complete, the cosmological time and BH entropy are reset to zero, and black hole growth begins again.

Similarly to the Standard Model of Cosmology, the Big Bang for each cycle of the universe is assumed to have occurred everywhere with widely separated observers reaching similar conclusions as regards its observed size, mass, and evolution. Unlike inflation theory [79–81], the VEP occurs prior to the Big Bang, and it is a time reversed interval spanning 26 *Gyr*. In contrast to CCC, BH disintegration occurs with great rapidity in our model compared to Hawking radiation [82, 83], and a mass fade-out [84] involving the disappearance of massive particles during BH evaporation has no significant role to play within the predicted age of an aeon. However, the CUBH may have observable black hole disintegration signatures from the last aeon similarly to Hawking disks predicted for CCC for which some evidence is given in [85]. While it is not clear whether such signatures could survive the VEP in our model, the cosmological time and entropy profiles in Fig. 12 offer compelling evidence for a cyclic universe, and the residual for ordinary matter $M_{om}(\epsilon_{ms})$, determined at the singularity of the current aeon, allows us to accurately predict MDPs for the next cycle. The cosmic singularity at ϵ_{ms} lies in the distant future, or alternatively, in the past prior to the Big Bang; therefore, it is hidden from observers and satisfies Penrose's cosmic censorship conjecture [86, 87]. Ordinary matter is uniformly distributed at the end of the VEP, thermalized, and the

Table VI. Aeon time line.

Time (Gyr)	α	ϵ	Halo Radius(<i>Gly</i>)	Particle Horizon(<i>Gly</i>)	Event
0	0	0	0	0	Start of aeon (BB)
5.01E-05	2.91E-04	1.87E-08	4.86E-03	1.06e-04	Begin Matter Dominated Era
3.71E-4	9.17E-4	1.85E-7	1.53E-2	8.36E-4	Photon decoupling
0.41	0.08	0.002	1.38	1.15	Max Matter MDP (Ω_m)
10.29	0.77	0.13	12.88	32.53	Begin DE Dominated Era
13.78	1	0.22	16.67	46.09	Current epoch/ <i>CEH</i> (t_o)
14.51	1.05	0.24	17.53	49.19	<i>CEH</i> (t_∞)
14.71	1.07	0.25	17.76	50.05	SU Halo Radius
26.01	2.13	1	35.52	116.28	Mass singularity/Start of VEP
0.11 \rightarrow 0 †	2.75	5/3	45.85	87.1 \rightarrow 0 ‡	End of aeon (BB)

† Final time at end of aeon is set to zero assuming H_{ms} from Eq. (133).

‡ Final particle horizon may be reset to zero since there are no observable structures in the VEP.

Figure 12. (a) Cosmological time, and (b) Black hole universe entropy over duration of aeon.

total BH mass is zero at the next Big Bang; therefore, each BB constitutes a low entropy state [88–90].

Conservation of energy is a key assumption in our theory for the redistribution of vacuum energy. The change in DE and the DM-DE interaction as the universe expands is offset by the increase in DM so the net vacuum energy within the halo radius of an aeon is zero. The energy lost in the red shift of light during expansion is supposed to be redistributed into vacuum energy; to make this plausible, consider two closely spaced parallel and perfectly reflecting plates in a Casimir-like experiment and introduce a suitably prepared system of photons between the plates of sufficient energy density/pressure to separate the plates to infinity: Work is done, and the photons lose energy; equivalently, the positive energy of the photons adds to the energy deficit between the plates until the net energy density in the gap is zero. Although negative energy modes are not directly observable, we are compelled to admit their existence based on their success in explaining the cosmological vacuum and the quantum

vacuum of stabilized QFT.

In sharp contrast to singularities in QFT processes, black hole singularities redistribute vacuum energy over vast distances; this leads to a small $\Lambda_o \propto R_{aeon}^{-2}$ in Eq. (96). No significant contribution to Λ_o is expected from quantum effects since singular processes in QFT only redistribute vacuum energy over infinitesimal distances, and the net energy density of the quantum vacuum is zero.

If an isolated BH of known mass is not feeding, then the spacetime characterized by a Schwarzschild or Kerr metric is static, and energy is globally conserved. For a galactic black hole that is actively feeding, the halo radius grows, orbits change, and the universe expands as vacuum energy is being redistributed; therefore, the energy of an orbiting star will be time dependent, but the total energy of the universe is conserved when we account for changes in vacuum energy. The spacetime associated with our CUBH has a time-translation symmetry in the sense that MDP measurements performed at an epoch in

Figure 13. Local Hubble constant dependence on erred H_0 .

the current aeon will yield the same results as a similar experiment at the same time in the next aeon.

Based on the cyclic universe's success in predicting MDPs from the residual mass $M_{om}(\epsilon_{ms})$ for ordinary matter and the content of the quantum and cosmological vacua, there appears to be no evidence to support the idea that matter and antimatter were created in equal

amounts in a Big Bang. On the other hand, the agreement between predictions of the theory and observations support the hypothesis that the vacuum consists of equal amounts of negative energy matter in DM and positive energy antimatter in DE. However, there might exist another universe in a larger cosmology where antimatter dominates, but that would require a vacuum where matter and antimatter were interchanged relative to that defined in [10].

In this theory it is unlikely that dark matter will be detected as a new particle since it is an unobservable constituent of the vacuum composed of all particles of the Standard Model, but having negative energy and positive pressure just the opposite of dark energy. It will be doubly hard to detect since negative energy particles don't interact with ordinary matter of which detectors are made.

In a CUBH, the source of CMB temperature variations may depend on the distribution of black holes, ordinary matter, and voids in the previous aeon, but that is a subject for future work.

The results provide a compelling explanation for the origin of dark energy and dark matter, flat galactic rotation curves, matter density parameters, Hubble tension, low Big Bang entropy, and the physics that drives the evolution of the universe.

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